

INTELLECTUAL AND IMMATERIAL BANK

BY WISE JESTER

ANNA ZAYTSEVA

wisejester@intellectualandimmaterialbank.com

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Briefly about IIB by Wise Jester

IIB is a GAME to train risk taking and collaboration skills of independent professionals across the “safe” borders of their environments, by letting them step into the unknown in a safely assisted manner. The users are independent professionals, always. They receive *just enough information* to decide if to connect or not. Their decisions shall change the picture of needs in their environments, and that will affect the others.

The game begins with showing any independent professional how s/he naturally thinks in situations of uncertainty and clashes of contexts, while being disconnected from the regular context – for avoidance of any social pressure. That guarantees purity of the results, which show to the person how that person naturally reacts towards breaches of the “normal”, predictable, unquestionable, common, plain, regular... in an own way.

It is painful to realize that a decision, which you took in a situation of uncertainty towards something new, was wrong. IIB begins with simulating such patterns through your own humor appreciation. Thereby, you can see your own personal decision-making pattern under the pressure of uncertainty early. Also, you can build up your connections with other people, intellectually and knowledgewise compatible with you and partly different. Both sides will be mutually challenged – by each other.

Also, in IIB, you are encouraged to have your own vision.

The problem context which demands IIB

Independent professional is not seen as a main economic unit. In the current monetary system, it is organization that is an economic unit. Existing solutions that focus on **independent professionals** treat them as “**resources**”, and that is why we have the very phenomenon of “Human Resources” as mediators. Most of Psychometrics, which HR apply, are not based on science, although certified by DNV GL (source: professional workshop on Psychometrics by Tor Åge Eikerapen from Skageike AS in Kristiansand, 30 August 2019). We would have never known this if we wouldn't have heard it from the first mouth at a seminar for 500 Euro.

THREE unseparated problems in one! It is called a “wicked problem”. In depth, the problems communicate:

Meanwhile, even if **organization is the main and core economic unit** of the actual monetary system, a HR consultant and partner at M.M.N. AS says: “Organizations are chaoses!” Considering this, how and why would you **place independent professionals into these?**

Even existing AI algorithms are made to take the **organizational side only**. Technology Review (23 June 2021) states: “Most matching engines [...] generate [...] their recommendations on three categories of data: [...] and behavioral data, like how often a user responds to messages or interacts with job postings.” What is the correlation between your interaction with someone's job postings and the depth of your mind, may we ask? Zero. That is a problem. You should be able to take your time to respond to any messages. That means being human – conscious thinking takes much more time than instant, superficial, autopilot thinking.

The phenomenon of “independent professional” is not less complex than “chaos” of organization. Both “independent” and “professional” are problems. According to the famous psychological experiment by Stanley Milgram (1963), **65% of people are conformists: they accept the social pressure on their individual decision making**, including that in the **professional dimension**.

Real feedback illustrating the problems: how in the interconnected world we need blind disconnection for quality and progress

I sent a connection request on LinkedIn to a manager/partner of an organization.

The organization pitches itself like “Do you have an innovative idea? We are your partner in Innovation Finance, Grant, investment...”

I do not have any contacts with anybody at this organization from before. My profile was viewed back but not approved.

That made me more curious. I googled reviews. This is a print screen of 1 out of 2 reviews that I could find.

glassdoor.com/Overview/Working-at-Innovayt-El_IE1010605.11,19.htm

Overview ▾ 2 Reviews -- Jobs 3 Salaries 1 Interviews 2 Benefits -- Photos

Innovayt Overview

Work Here? Get a Free Employer Account

Website:	www.innovayt.eu	Headquarters:	Copenhagen, Denmark
Size:	1 to 50 Employees	Founded:	null
Type:	Company - Private	Revenue:	Unknown / Non-Applicable

Competitors: UNKNOWN

Innovayt Reviews

3.0 ★★★★★ ▾

0% Recommend to a Friend

3.0 ★★★★★ ▾

Current Employee, more than 3 years

"Too much pressure, work/life balance is something not real and micromangement by the book"

May 14, 2021 - Project Developer in Braga

✗ Doesn't Recommend ✓ Positive Outlook

Pros

Nice and highly skilled colleagues, almost all have a PhD. It used to have a good environment between colleagues and there have been always some celebration parties once nice results and key

Cons

Favouritism due to the existence of personal friends within the company (so lower chances to advance on your career if you do not intend to be personal friend with anyone from the management team).

Advice to Management

As the company grew, the need for an HR is essential! You cannot rely on partners to play this role, otherwise it will be always played on favouritism, which is the current situation. Treat your

How IIB untangles the wicked problem

In contrast to the conventional monetary system, **independent professional** for IIB is **NOT a resource**, but a **conscious, sustainable human who can decide**. Most of Psychometrics, which the HR mediators use, are intuitive, interpretive, casual and situational, but the unique humor-based module of IIB is science-based.

HR are expensive and sometimes call organizations “chaos”. IIB removes mediators between independent professionals and organizations. Basically, IIB is not about organizations at all. IIB trains risk taking **by making independent professionals step into a large blind network and apply their collaboration skill, in computationally assisted compatibility** which reduces that risk, to focus jointly on their visions.

The existing computationally assisted tools are biased in favor of organizations, as it was already mentioned. Independent professionals are taught unconditional obedience to get a job – we cannot call it otherwise when HR consultants tell you “sell yourself”. In IIB, the **combinations between and among independent professionals and collaborations target their intellectual harmony, in symmetry between both sides.**

Independent professionals are susceptible to social pressure on their decision making. IIB disintegrates them from their social contexts to show them their actual deeper and instant thinking, so kissing up is physically eliminated. Also, IIB is an ultimate supporter of **hybrid-knowledge collaborations and minds, yet exotic – for they create novel solutions spontaneously because of being AWARE.**

Wise Jester is in the process of joining the EU movement of **data-ownership return to people. You own your data and use it in IIB. That is a steel grounding principle.**

and creates opportunities!

Moreover!

The image shows a Google search interface. At the top left is the Google logo. The search bar contains the text "how many people hate their jobs" and has a close button (X) and a search icon (magnifying glass). Below the search bar are navigation options: "Alle" (selected), "Bilder", "Nyheter", "Videoer", "Maps", "Mer", "Innstillinger", and "Verktøy". The search results show "Omtrent 687 000 000 resultater (0,72 sekunder)". The main result is a snippet from Staff Squared: "A global poll conducted by Gallup has uncovered that out of **the** world's one billion full-time workers, only 15% of **people** are engaged at work. That means that an astronomical 85% of **people** are unhappy in **their jobs**." The date "3. des. 2019" is shown below the snippet. To the right of the text is a small image of a man with glasses sitting at a desk, looking thoughtful with his hand to his face. Below the snippet is the URL "https://www.staffsquared.com > blog > why-85-of-people-...", the title "Why 85% of People Hate their Jobs | Staff Squared", and two links: "Informasjon om sammendrag av søkeresultater" and "Tilbakemelding". At the bottom, there is a section titled "Folk spør også om dette" with a result "Does everyone hate their job?" and a dropdown arrow.

Google

how many people hate their jobs

Alle Bilder Nyheter Videoer Maps Mer Innstillinger Verktøy

Omtrent 687 000 000 resultater (0,72 sekunder)

A global poll conducted by Gallup has uncovered that out of **the** world's one billion full-time workers, only 15% of **people** are engaged at work. That means that an astronomical 85% of **people** are unhappy in **their jobs**.

3. des. 2019

<https://www.staffsquared.com > blog > why-85-of-people-...>

[Why 85% of People Hate their Jobs | Staff Squared](#)

Informasjon om sammendrag av søkeresultater • Tilbakemelding

Folk spør også om dette

Does everyone hate their job?

Also...

Survey: 40% of employees are thinking of quitting their jobs

Research shows bosses need to do more to support 18-25 year olds. Image: Unsplash/Tim van der Kuip

World Economic Forum “More than half of Generation Z workers are considering resigning”

02 Jun 2021

Sean Fleming

This article is part of the [The Jobs Reset Summit](#)

...and freelancers, again?

Google search: how many freelancers in the world

1.1 billion freelancers

With a total **global** workforce of around 3.5 billion, there are about 1.1 billion **freelancers** around the **world**. There were 57 million **freelancers** working from home in 2019.

<https://ddiy.co> › freelance-statistics

54 Freelance Statistics, Trends, and Insights [Updated for 2021]

🔍 Informasjon om sammendrag av søkeresultater • 🗨️ Tilbakemelding

Competitors?

Upwork (856,269 followers on Facebook, 828,261 on LinkedIn; USA): posts photos of freelancers, a list of their skills, with the stars they received like products on Amazon, and a price tag per hour. Not automated.

Fiverr (2,162,931 followers on Facebook, 6 companies called “Fiverr” on LinkedIn, and I don’t understand which one is the one; Israel): is focused on artistic freelancers like visual designers. Not automated.

Toptal (371,372 followers on Facebook, 221,553 followers on LinkedIn; USA): picks up former employees with 5+ years of experience and backgrounds at places like Stanford University, IBM, Google, Microsoft, NASA, and Amazon, and promises best match to your project. Not automated.

Insolvo (27 followers on Facebook, 5 followers on LinkedIn; Estonia): promises to hire freelancers for you in a speedy and safe way, and in best match, too. AI-powered.

They solve normal problems, not wicked problems

Centrally and manually, they approve professionals, with price tags per hour against their profile picture, so you can pick the one you like most

The image shows two side-by-side Upwork freelancer profiles. Each profile includes a circular profile picture, a title, a name, a list of skills in pill-shaped buttons, a short bio, a 'Read more' link, an hourly rate with an information icon, a star rating with the number of reviews, a location, and a green 'Get Started' button.

Stephanie W.
Customer Insights Freelancer
Skills: Customer Insights, Consulting, Newsletter, Blog Writing, Brand Management, Management Skills, Social Media Posts
Bio: I am the Social Media Manager that will get you results.
Rate: \$80/hr
Rating: 5.0/5 (23 reviews)
Location: United States, Delray Beach

Roxana G.
Customer Insights Freelancer
Skills: Customer Insights, Branding, UX Design, sketch app, Wireframing, Adobe Photoshop, Vector Graphics
Bio: UX designer with background on UI design and illustration. I have 5 years of experience working as a multidisciplinary design.
Rate: \$45/hr
Rating: 4.9/5 (13 reviews)
Location: United States, Jefferson

Folk spør også om dette

Google search: upwork review

What is better than Upwork?

Are there better alternatives to Upwork?

Is Upwork dying?

Upwork is dead after they have made it to where you pay for connects, and limited invites for freelancers. Stephane is trying to squeeze out all the money he can from freelancers. 20% fee for small jobs, \$1 for connects and now limited invites. 1. jul. 2019

<https://www.reddit.com> > [Upwork](#) > [comments](#) > [upwork_...](#)

[Upwork is dead 2019 : Upwork - Reddit](#)

Jane Waterson

Hi there, I have tried to close my Upwork account but receiving a message saying 'At this time we are unable to close your account. Please call our concierge team at 1-866-676-3375, select option 3, and we will help you close your account.'. I'm outside the US, tried the number not working. Can't see an email address on your website, can someone please help me?

Like · Reply · 18 h

 View 1 more reply

Edmond Dantes

Why do you want to close your Upwork account?
Now I'm trying to create my Upwork account.
But you want my opposition, so just want to know why.
Could you please let me know if it is not a personal matter?

Like · Reply · 8 h

**Facebook:
Upwork**

Facebook: Fiverr

Fiverr 23 June at 18:03 · 🌐

It's Drag Queen Story Hour! Today we have special guest Lil Miss Hot Mess who will be reading Fiverr's first LGBTQ+ children's book "Sea The Love" and her very own book, "The Hips on the Drag Queen go Swish, Swish, Swish." Come join us as we share the import... See more

84 29 comments 2 shares

Like Comment Share

Most relevant

Write a comment...

Sarim Ali
Hello
I got Promoted Gigs feature from Fiverr.
But now it's Disabled.why this is disabled please tell me... See more
Unhide · 1 d

Gabriel Acevedo Olvera
Another company promoting sickness, how awful, and not respecting the kids. How in the world this is a benefit for the little ones. Madness.
Like · Reply · 1 d

Shaun Folkwein
No one was asking what it was, we know what it is and we're asking that you stop with it.
Like · Reply · 2 d

...and they may use trends in the popular culture and political agendas to attract attention

Facebook: Fiverr

Fiverr 21 May · 🌐

From smallest to tallest, could you put these buildings in order? 🤔🏢

Get your project off the ground with detailed plans, 3D models, and more: <https://fvrr.co/3oKi3LK>

Put these buildings in order of height.

Makkah Royal Clock Tower | Burj Khalifa | Shanghai Tower | Empire State Building | The Shard

97 36 comments 3 shares

Like Comment Share

Most relevant

Areeba Gurya
Its been days didn't fiver CS did not resolve my issue. Everytime they went unresponsive for days.
Completely helpless my ticket number is #5651614
Like · Reply · 6 w

Fiverr (2,162,931 followers on Facebook, 6 companies called "Fiverr" on LinkedIn)

Leon Wyczółkowski "Stańczyk" (1898)

Also, why would they sell brands?

...the brands of the big names behind the professionals as their former employees, not really the brands of the very professionals

Ruth Madrigal
Scrum Master
Previously at **IBM**

Emily Dubow
UX/UI Designer
Previously at **Samsung**

Vladimir Mitrovic
C# Developer
Previously at **Apple**

Anis Arman
I check many platforms to find best developer but I can't from under a "Sponsored" post

Can a startup afford one from IBM?
And why "previously"?

Facebook: Toptal
Anis Arman: I check many platforms to find best developer but I can't from under a "Sponsored" post
Noam Bayun: Well since I didn't study at Google or work at Stanford I guess I'm out ...

Toptal (371,372 followers on Facebook, 221,553 followers on LinkedIn; USA)

Also, why would they sell brands?

...the brands of the big names behind the professionals as their former employees,
not really the brands of the very professionals

Yeah, but...

**“Sometimes it is the people
no one can imagine
anything of
who do the things no one
can imagine.” Alan Turing**

Can a startup afford one from IBM?

And why “previously”?

Facebook:
Toptal

Anis Arman
I check many platforms to find best developer but I can't
from under a “Sponsored” post

Joam Bayun
Well since I didn't study at Google or work at Stanford I guess I'm out ...
Like · Reply · 19 w

Toptal (371,372 followers
on Facebook, 221,553
followers on LinkedIn; USA)

And would these be from the measurement side, perhaps?

IIB:

- Science-based, humor-driven
- Symmetry between individuals and groups of individuals
- Both are “at the edge of chaos”
- No mediators in between
- No statuses and facial data
- Data is owned by the users
- Focused on hybrid knowledge and clashes in minds
- Hybrid between automation and manual choice making

More about the seriousness of the demand and its scale

47% of jobs will vanish in the next 25 years (Oxford University), however, the learning culture in the society is weak: **only 2% adult population per 1 mil. are open to learn** (Jon Ivar Johansen, "Endringskoden"), that is only **15 mil. people** out of **741 mil. people** in Europe

RED: a share of users in direct need
GREEN: a share of users genuinely interested

employment should be a basic human right (Big Think)

...but **85% of people hate their jobs**, approx. **leave rate per org because of conflicts is 45%** that is **13k Euro per person**

6 out of 10 organizations digitize (Central Office of Statistics, Norway): that means **60% processes in org are change processes**, but **betw. 50 and 90% people prefer staying in their comfort zones!**

min. 20% of empl. are self-employments (varies regionally; **30% in US in May 2020, Forbes**): that highlights the share of independent professionals

professions in hybrid knowledge emerge: e.g. operator of automated tools, healthcare engineer, behavior analyst, data-driven life coach, robot dispatcher, whereas appr. **75% of organizations fail because of not seeing own weaknesses**

No government is prepared (The Economist)

"The best companies create a market." David Rusenko, founder of Weebly

When an accelerator asks you about your competitors, feel free to pick up the best quote as a reply or create yours!

Business for Punks

BAKE YOUR OWN GODDAMN PIE

If anyone ever tells you to look for a gap in the market, tell them to go to hell. Why anyone would want to do something that stupid is beyond me. The illusive gap that we should all apparently plug is a quick-fire route to nowhere.

The whole gap-in-the-market approach is an outdated fallacy that should be burnt and banished from history. It was probably thought up by a 'business' academic who has never even started a stamp-collecting club, never mind a business.

Don't look for gaps in the market. Don't be a pathetic leech scrambling around for crumbs off someone else's second-rate pie. Bake your own goddamn pie. Look to create a whole new market. Start a category, not a business. Be a fish in a tiny self-built pond, then grow that pond. If you swim in someone else's pond, you will just get gobbled up.

You have to narrow your focus to such an extent that there is no current market for what you are about to do. This gives you the amazing opportunity to create a whole new category. Then you can focus on growing the category rather than just differentiating your brand from the others. To be credible, your reason to exist needs to extend beyond your own brand, and a focus on growing a brand-new emerging category you are passionate about instantly gives you wider credibility and relevance. We are not about growing BrewDog, we are about getting more people to drink great beer. Period.

GoPro did not just make a video camera. They did not look for a gap in the existing camera market. They did not want to offer existing cam-

Starting a Business for Vagabond Vigilantes

era customers something slightly better than they already had. They wanted to sell a new type of camera to a completely new audience. They created a whole new category and pioneered tiny HD cameras for extreme sports enthusiasts and built an amazing business in the process.

The power of any brand is inversely proportional to its scope; consequently your focus should be laser-like and your product should be uber-tuned. Then you have the inviting task of creating a brand and defining your own market. Don't scramble around begging for other people's leftovers: create your own rules and you exist in your own space.

**"Business for Punks"
James Watt, co-founder of Brewdog**

**THE WHOLE GAP-IN-THE-MARKET
APPROACH IS AN OUTDATED
FALLACY THAT SHOULD BE BURNT
AND BANISHED FROM HISTORY.**

"Competition is for losers." Peter Thiel, co-founder of PayPal, Palantir Technologies, Founders Fund, the 1st outside investor in Facebook

"The artist always creates from scratch, from nothing. Only his imagination works. You must create a character on your own. All by yourself – from the beginning till the end. All by yourself. Then the character will be alive."

Anatoly M. Savchenko (1924-2011), Soviet animator and illustrator

*A wise man once said,
"Bees don't waste their
time explaining to flies that
honey is better than shit."
Read that again.*

*a casual
Internet wisdom*

-UNKNOWN | @THESPIRITUALMAGIC

"Almost every book, article, blog, video and speech on innovation starts with the premise that the key to innovation is to "solve a problem" or "identify an unmet need" or "do a gap analysis" or "invent a painkiller for a significant pain" or, one of my favorites, "address a hair-on-fire problem." [...] The key to big Innovation is finding big Opportunities, not solving big Problems. If you deconstruct the path to innovation that most successful high tech companies have taken, you see that the big leap was not analysis – figuring out what was wrong that needed to be fixed.

Rather, the big leap was synthesis – seeing how all of the other innovations in the market created an opportunity to create a new wave of innovation. [...] If you are looking for problems to solve, you are probably looking backward, not forward. You are forcing yourself into the mindset of the current way of doing things. This is the mindset behind the quip: If we asked people in 1900 how to improve transportation, they would have said they wanted faster horses. The question to ask is not, what is a problem that we can fix? The question is, how can we leverage new technologies to enable something better? This is the Opportunity Mindset." Bill Reichert "The Language of Innovation is Wrong", blog

In the Intellectual and Immaterial Bank:

- **The requestor and the requested are treated equally in weight, so both can decide. Their “meeting” in the blind ocean of other users is computationally assisted, based on their deeper reasoning and natural sense of comfort, which is unique for every person and group – for their complementation and mutual disruption or challenge;**
- **Nobody “sells” themselves or others, and, hereby, avoids hype; everyone in IIB is as they are;**
- **Because of that, IIB is blind to any status and facial data, and the users are presented with their “mohawks”;**
- **All users in IIB own their data and decide over their own data, not IIB or Wise Jester;**
- **IIB places its focus on the most interesting: where chaos meets order, or the true human side of us as people. In contrast to the reviewed “competitors”, I am aware that best match is unnatural, and it does not exist. We all have diverse complex strengths, and we change: evolve and increase entropy. Today you “match”, tomorrow no longer: and that is natural! Spontaneity makes us ourselves. IIB considers that and places all “at the edge of chaos”.**

IIB is hybrid between automation and manual choice making, where both sides can decide upon their involvement, if they share a vision, so they can really make a change by becoming change agents.

IIB is a complex, multi-conditional environment for triggering change agents to solve wicked problems.

What is “Wicked Problem”? Is it like “Wicked Game”?

In Complex Systems – patternwise knowledge about natural and artificial systems, time, adaptation, entropy, exchange of matter, energy and information – there is an understanding of Wicked Problems.

A wicked problem is when you realize that you are a part of it. You must change your behavior in order to change the context and, hereby, to solve the problem. If you cannot see yourself as a part of the problem, even when the problem is severe – it won't look like a problem to you. Like turd, being not a problem to a maggot, is a problem when on your shoe. Our world is dual. Nature is dual.

Let me describe a **mathematical system in plain words:**

Complexity is an opposite process to Entropy. Both co-begin each other.

Emergence is an opposite process to Wickedness. Both co-begin each other.

**Emergence is $1+1=3$ as more than a sum of all the parts. A child is emergent from a woman and a man.
All of them die eventually because of Entropy.**

For nature, that is one of many processes of adaptation in species. To be born, live and die is to behave like a change agent for the species and the environment.

IIB will help you to become a change agent and act like one while you live.

Wickedness is when you are a part of a problem, because that problem is seen as your normal environment. You cannot provide a normal, certain, conventional solution that would “fit” a wicked problem.

You must become a change agent to influence change in an environment. Wicked problems require values and integrity. IIB is a new HUMAN-2-HUMAN solution, which considers human complexity, imagination, and spontaneity. Individuals and groups are the subjects in IIB, so change agents and environments meet up in there.

IIB can be used by freelancers, but it is not made for them directly. IIB is for doers, not sellers of their time for money in no real vision. Doers can be among freelancers, but they can also be among those 85% of the entire population who hate their jobs. This is where the truly fun visions can be!

IIB provides opportunities for the doers to get “visible” and to be able to “see” other people. IIB strengthens their capacity to take risks in choice making, where no data about statuses or faces interferes. The final word is by the visions pitched, so a human can make a choice about another human or a group – to collaborate or not.

IIB is a game, and, in intellectual compatibility and challenge, you receive 3 out of 5 knowledge areas you requested, with the first one as obligatory. That makes IIB an ultimate facilitator for hybrid knowledge, yet exotic in contemporary organizations still interested in “best fit” which does not exist and paying HR for that. HR tend to reject people with hybrid knowledge because those do not fit job standards and ads. Hybrid competence makes brains extrapolate knowledge, recognize and compare patterns of ongoing, ended and starting processes, and more.

As a user of IIB, you are given choices of collaboration and people, compatible with you, and the knowledge you requested + new! This may make genuine wonders emerge, and you can start new processes: begin a hybrid solution of an emerging technology, develop unconventional methodologies, and create something beyond your expectations!

Briefly about opportunities that innovation may provide

Friar **experimenting, while Van Helsing comes into the lab**: I've got a few things. No, any idiot can make a sword. **collides with a guy holding a metal stick to make a sword of** Come along! Here, take this. Rings garlic, holy water, silver stage, crucifix... **suddenly, a machine gun on the background starts shooting**

Van Helsing: Why can't I have one of those?

"Van Helsing" (2004) by Stephen Sommers

Friar: You've never gone after vampires before now, have you?

Van Helsing: Vampires, gargoyles, warlocks, they're all the same. Best when cooked well.

Friar: No, they're not all the same. A vampire is nothing like a warlock. My granny could kill a warlock.

Van Helsing: Ha-ha. Carl, you've never even been out of the abbey. How do you know about vampires?

Friar: I read. Oh, here's something new. **comes up to a barrel of pale liquid** Glycerin 48. **takes a drop sample and throws it on the floor, what leads to an explosion** Sorry! **apologizes to the disturbed people around**

People: What's wrong with you?!

Friar to Van Helsing: The air around here is thick with envy. Ah, this is my latest invention. **takes out a machine-like arbalest** It's gas-propelled. Capable of catapulting arrows in rapid succession... at tremendous velocity. Just pull the trigger and hold on. I've heard the stories from Transylvania. Trust me, you'll need this. A work of certifiable genius.

Friar: I'm a veritable cornucopia of talent.

Van Helsing: Did you invent this? **sees a device looking like this*

*and grabs it**

Friar: I've been working on that for 12 years. **tries to get it back** It's compressed magma from Mount Vesuvius... with pure alkaline from the Gobi Desert. It's one of a kind.

Van Helsing: What's it for?

“Van Helsing” (2004) by Stephen Sommers

Friar: I don't know, but I'm sure it'll come in handy.

Van Helsing: Twelve years, and you don't know what it does?

Friar: I didn't say that. I said I didn't know what it's for. What it does is to create a light source... equal to the intensity of the sun.

Van Helsing: This will come in handy how?

Friar: I don't know. You can blind your enemies. Charbroil a herd of charging wildebeest. Use your imagination.

Van Helsing: No, I'm gonna use yours. That's why you're coming with me.

Friar: [... ..] be [.....] I am!

Van Helsing: You cursed! Not very well. You're a monk. You shouldn't curse at all.

Friar: Actually, I'm still just a friar. I can curse all I want! [... ..]! **smiles mysteriously**

friar

...compared with what experts may say about innovation

Frank Sinatra: “Rock ‘n’ Roll is phony. It’s sung, written and played by cretinous goons.”

Ken Olson, CEO of DEC: “There is no reason anyone would want a computer in their home.”

Ernst Werner von Siemens: “Electric light will never take the place of gas.”

William Thomson Kelvin: “Radio has no future.” “X-rays will prove to be a hoax.”

Harry Morris Warner of Warner Brothers: “Who the hell wants to hear actors talk?”

Rex Lambert: “Television won’t matter in your lifetime or mine.”

Herbert Wells: “I refuse to see any sort of submarine doing anything except suffocating its crew and floundering at sea.”

Albert Einstein: “There is not the slightest indication that nuclear energy will ever be obtainable. It would mean that the atom would have to be shattered at will.”

“The 20 worst assumptions made by experts”, Paul Sloane

<https://www.destination-innovation.com/the-20-worst-assumptions-made-by-experts/>

Jan Matejko "Stańczyk" (1862)

Wise Jester

Jim Morrison, The Doors:

“I've noticed that when people are joking, they're usually dead serious, and when they're serious, they're usually pretty funny.”

Why humor?

Humor is a special area of cognitive science. Humor is about clashing situations that relate. Brain “solves” a joke and rewards itself with a smile or laugh, which cannot be faked. Humor is based on re-composition of what people know and can synthesize, when they “crack” the code of a joke by getting it. Considering that jokes demonstrate a rich diversity, individual appreciation of humor is naturally unique. To collaborate is a process and a skill, exploring a balance between certainty and uncertainty, compatibility and challenge. Humor code-cracking qualities give a great clue about it!

Your capacities

Your strongest capacity for making change is **proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon**.

While thinking, you are rather after **imagination**.
You tend to react immediately to **social signals**.
You prefer working in **low-pressure contexts**.

- preferred comfort zones
 - Low-pressure contexts
 - Contexts with high uncertainty
 - Collectivistic environments
 - High-pressure contexts
 - Independent genre
- instant-th. triggers
 - Social signals
 - Cognitive signals
 - Emotional signals
 - Knowledge
 - Focused aim
- deep-th. triggers
 - Solidarity with the others
 - Imagination
 - Coming up with alternatives
 - Faster taking the new into practice
- capacities for transformation
 - Having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis
 - Proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon
 - Breaking the old things down faster
 - Standing for flat collaboration of hybrid competencies

Needs of your collaboration

Your collaboration may have a challenge with **structures and processes that are stuck**.

Your collaboration may experience **ignoring uniqueness**.
Your collaboration might be overlooking **how the others feel**.
Your collaboration disrupts comfort zones by expecting **individual initiative**.

- disruption of comfort
 - Pressuring the members
 - Demanding clarity and plan
 - Expecting individual initiative
 - Slowing down for well-ordered actions
 - Accountability and transparency
- tendency to ignore
 - The socially accepted
 - Facts and numbers
 - How the others feel
 - Siloed thinking
 - Being too dispersed
- intellectual depth
 - Ignoring uniqueness
 - Being too down-to-earth
 - Structures and processes that are stuck
 - Fear of difference and novelty
- needs in transformation
 - Seeing the big picture
 - Obvious needs in new, unknown ideas
 - Degree of inner passion of the member
 - Potential for synergic collaboration

What can the humor module do?

In IIB, humor “does” unique user-data generation, computed to show the professionals their own unique way of thinking where contexts collide. Properly argued and anchored in Humor Science, the module shows you your instinctive (immediate, instant) thinking and conscious (aware, deeper) thinking, beautifully theorized by Daniel Kahneman, who got a Nobel prize in behavioral economics for that. The theory was further developed by a humor scientist Larry Ventis, and his peers in Cognitive science, Linguistics, Psychology, Behaviorism, and more. Also, that theory was accurately applied by Jon Ivar Johansen to explore change processes in organizations, starting from individuals. Compiled in a unique way with practice, the elements of the accumulated knowledge emerged into a synthesized, relationship-intensive module in IIB, full of mathematical calculations, created and applied by the founder of Wise Jester. Mathematically and computationally, IIB considers the tendency of the human mind to equilibrium and, also, values its natural “edge of chaos”, including such features as imagination and spontaneity.

A permanent link to a document with the relevant science extracts:
<https://zenodo.org/record/4724974>

Why shall that computational thing be so black and blind?

Young Alan Turing **while solving crosswords**: What's that you're reading?

Christopher Morcom: It's about cryptography.

Young Alan Turing: Like secret messages?

Christopher Morcom: Not secret. That's the brilliant part. Messages that anyone can see but no one knows what they mean, unless you have the key.

Young Alan Turing: How's that different from talking?

Christopher Morcom: Talking?

Young Alan Turing: When people talk to each other, they never say what they mean, they say something else. And you're expected to just know what they mean. Only I never do. So... How's that different?

Because, just like on LinkedIn, there are so many honored speakers and experts that we usually have difficulties seeing the true gems: not those who know much, but those who are open, have imagination, consciousness, integrity, and guts to use that.

Also, return to slide 4.

Christopher Morcom: Alan, I have a funny feeling you're going to be very good at this. **gives Alan a book "A Guide to Codes and Spheres" as a gift**

"The Imitation Game" (2014) by Morten Tyldum

...when LinkedIn leaked...

Interesting Engineering ✓
1 July at 05:30 · 🌐

Facebook

That's more than 92% of the total 756 million LinkedIn users. 🐱
#engineering

INTERESTINGENGINEERING.COM

A Second Massive LinkedIn Breach Exposes the Data of 700M Users
That's the second massive breach for the company in less than three months. Ouch!

👍🤔😱 1K 149 comments 337 shares

👍 Like 💬 Comment ➦ Share

 Nikola Šever
This happens once a month for LinkedIn. Is this even a news 😏. I only wish that the ones who stole the data need an ambitious electrical engineer, team player, willing to learn... 🤖
Like · Reply · 3 d 👍👍 99
↳ 3 replies

 Harold Von Leighton
Time to leave that useless platform, a hotbed for egoistic salary people and self proclaimed 'experts' and 'leaders' who flaunt their titles and nothing else.
Like · Reply · 3 d · Edited 👍👍 40
↳ 2 replies

 Ernest Getwell 👑 Top fan
I can see the end if "centralized" social media is coming. Nothing more is better than the upcoming decentralized platforms.
Like · Reply · 3 d 👍 1

 Stephen Lau
But a lot of contents from the Linkedins are inflated, exaggerated, n even made up. The ego n misrepresentations are readily spotted especially in cases where u know that individual, their history n personality. So not much of a data breach for the 700M
Like · Reply · 3 d 👍 5

Why is IIB h2h? Why without faces? Why computational?

Alan Turing :

The interesting question is, just because something thinks differently from you, does that mean it's not thinking? We allow that humans have such divergences from one another. You like strawberries. I hate ice-skating. You cry at sad films. I'm allergic to pollen. What does it mean to have different tastes — different preferences — other than to say that our brains work differently? That we think differently from one another?

And if we can say that about each other, why can't we say the same for brains made of copper and steel?

“The Imitation Game” (2014) by Morten Tyldum

A most recent pick by a Norwegian innovation accelerator and VC fund for Autumn 2021 was a housing company.

On phone, the founder of the accelerator told me:

What is the most common job in Norway? **We pick only what we understand.** ^

The Most In-Demand Jobs and How Much They Pay

Job	NOK	USD
Waiter	391,360	42,225
Plumber	381,520	41,160
Electrician	405,390	43,740
Mechanic	401,495	43,320

14 rader til • 19. aug. 2020

A local Experienced Serial Entrepreneur, as his status on LinkedIn says, writes to me:

"A computational humor-based change agent" does not give me any idea what you are doing. It is like talking a language I do not understand – and I definitely do not grasp what this is... :) sorry.

That is why from the start I am not focusing on the national level

A Chairman of the Board of a Norwegian state-owned VC Fund writes on his LinkedIn wall:

Norway is experiencing ever-accelerating change as we move towards a post-oil world.

Is it hard to find a job in Norway? ^

Norway has been ranked as the most attractive country for migrant workers in Scandinavia. But that doesn't mean it's easy to get a job. The key message to take on board is that unless you work extremely hard to integrate yourself into Norwegian culture, your job prospects will be limited. 20. sep. 2013

<https://www.thelocal.no> > how-to-get-a-job-in-norway

FEATURE: How to get a job in Norway - The Local

...meanwhile on IIB

What are the domains of your professional interests formal and informal? Choose 5.
You can select what have you studied, worked with and are curios of, and what you simply love.

Physics Engineering Statistics Math XR Robotics Coding Regulation
Economics Gaming Entrepreneurship User experience Social work Writing
Music Complex systems Hybrid innovation Communication Arts Sports
Medicine Blockchain Environment Audiovisual works

DONE!

You own your data. You get a punk "mohawk" of your cognitive uniqueness, which is your only picture that other users can "see". You use your mohawk to build up your de facto collaborations or to attract those. IIB is a blind gamified network. The last say between you and others will have a shared vision.

BEGIN AS AN INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONAL

BEGIN AS AN AUTHOR OF A COLLABORATION

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If Tolstoy and Dostoevsky could have met, they would have written "War and Idiots".

4/36

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I wonder, where did people cough before theater was invented?

6/36

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One man treated everything with humor and died of laughter.

15/36

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[BEGIN AS AN INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONAL](#)

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INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONAL IS A USER UNIT IN IIB

[blind search results]

This is you

Your strongest capacity for making change is **having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis.**

While thinking, you are rather after **imagination.**

You tend to react immediately to **cognitive signals.**

You prefer working in **collectivistic environments.**

Pitched: I am diligent and good at executing difficult tasks. I want to work on truly groundbreaking projects.

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

Username: jahgwhj81k1

The highest need in change of this collaboration is **degree of inner passion of the members.**

What would be comfortable to you in this collaboration is **pressuring the members.**

This collaboration has an intellectual challenge in **being too down-to-earth.**

The competencies, which this collaboration has for you, are: **engineering.**

The unique competencies, which you can develop at this collaboration, are: **physics, regulation, economics, entrepreneurship.**

Pitched: Our collaboration solves the problem of plastic waste, and we are looking for more concerned people.

Username: degjwytq652

The highest need in change of this collaboration is **fear of difference and novelty.**

What would be comfortable to you in this collaboration is **pressuring the members.**

This collaboration has an intellectual challenge in **being too down-to-earth.**

The competencies, which this collaboration has for you, are: **math, xr, statistics.**

The unique competencies, which you can develop at this collaboration, are: **entrepreneurship, complex systems.**

Pitched: We are developing novel healthcare solutions, with public-sector actors and civilians involved.

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

Username: wqlwji6781

The highest need in change of this collaboration is **degree of inner passion of the members.**

What would be comfortable to you in this collaboration is **pressuring the members.**

This collaboration has an intellectual challenge in **being too down-to-earth.**

The competencies, which this collaboration has for you, are: **math, user experience.**

The unique competencies, which you can develop at this collaboration, are: **hybrid innovation, complex systems, entrepreneurship.**

Pitched: Our team consists of developers, and we are looking for more designers, who will have a sense of style and beauty.

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

[Feature update from June 22, 2021]

WHO CAN LOOK FOR ANY COLLABORATIONS AT ANY TIME

...AND FOR OTHER INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONALS

Your strongest capacity for making change is **proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon.**
 While thinking, you are rather after **imagination.**
 You tend to react immediately to **social signals.**
 You prefer working in **low-pressure contexts.**
Pitched: I am a hopeless loser who is tired of bureaucrats and wants to build intelligence-intensive mechatronic solutions of tomorrow.

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

[blind search results]

Username: dshwi363kshkytq65w33sd2kshu289hksqmbg891hjkshqlqqk
 This person is favorably complementing you in response to new situations by being rather sensitive to **emotional signals.**
 While thinking before doing, this person also goes for **focused aim.**
 The main strength of this person is in **having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis.**
 The competencies, which this person shares with your request, are primarily: **engineering, entrepreneurship, gaming, statistics.**
 The unique competencies, which this person can bring in, are: **physics.**
Pitched: I am crazy about math and physics, because we can make even more new solutions if we better understand Mother Nature!

Username: sjaqqkgjagd652o1hwekhsjgkah82o2tyuq2jgdqhgwhfqkjh
 This person is favorably complementing you in response to new situations by being rather sensitive to **emotional signals.**
 While thinking before doing, this person also goes for **imagination.**
 The main strength of this person is in **having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis.**
 The competencies, which this person shares with your request, are primarily: **engineering, entrepreneurship, statistics.**
 The unique competencies, which this person can bring in, are: **physics, robotics.**
Pitched: My main interest is emerging business models, and I would love to join a startup that works on a highly unique idea.

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

Username: qjgksjdjahgdw82632jgahfwhqjt2i1gsgdj1tidbj2tksvghj187ejs
 This person is favorably complementing you in response to new situations by being rather sensitive to **cognitive signals.**
 While thinking before doing, this person also goes for **focused aim.**
 The main strength of this person is in **breaking the old things down faster.**
 The competencies, which this person shares with your request, are primarily: **math, engineering.**
 The unique competencies, which this person can bring in, are: **complex systems, robotics, coding.**
Pitched: Robots are my everything. I worked in industrial robotics, and now I want to build a humanoid of my own.

[Feature update from June 22, 2021]

TO BUILD UP INTELLECTUALLY COMPATIBLE AND VISION-DRIVEN HYBRID-KNOWLEDGE COLLABORATIONS

AND ANY COLLABORATION AS A COLLECTIVE PICTURE CAN LOOK FOR ANY INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONALS

Needs of my collaboration

- Your collaboration may have a challenge with **structures and processes that are stuck.**
- Your collaboration may experience **being too dispersed.**
- Your collaboration might be overlooking the **socially accepted.**
- Your collaboration disrupts comfort zones by **pressuring the members.**

Pitched: Our team is looking for a bright developer who understands the social complexity around emerging technologies and can work fast.

DIRECTLY, WITHOUT MEDIATORS AND AT ANY TIME

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

Username: jywgejay2731kjqhwmai2u01lkqajy2g1jhqf62reamo03egh120
 The strongest capacity of this person for making change is **faster taking the new into practice.**
 To balance your work style, this person prefers working in **collectivistic environments.**
 When thinking over something in depth, this person goes for **solidarity with the others.**
 The competencies of this person, which you requested for your collaboration, are primarily: **coding, robotics.**
 The unique competencies, which this person can bring into your collaboration, are: **statistics, physics, engineering.**

Pitched: I am a Java developer, and I am available to become a part of a new environment. I love travelling too.

Username: sjghwja721klwjka89q2kajwhdjba827jhwekq3ryhjfqh62jq2g
 The strongest capacity of this person for making change is **proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon.**
 To balance your work style, this person prefers working in **high-pressure contexts.**
 When thinking over something in depth, this person goes for **imagination.**
 The competencies of this person, which you requested for your collaboration, are primarily: **xr, robotics.**
 The unique competencies, which this person can bring into your collaboration, are: **complex systems, entrepreneurship, engineering.**

Pitched: I am developing a new type of digital wallets. I am looking for collaborations that develop respective user applications.

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

Username: dshwi363kshkytq65w33sd2kshu289hksqmbg891hjkshqlqqk
 The strongest capacity of this person for making change is **breaking the old things down faster.**
 To balance your work style, this person prefers working in **contexts with high uncertainty.**
 When thinking over something in depth, this person goes for **focused aim.**
 The competencies of this person, which you requested for your collaboration, are primarily: **coding, robotics.**
 The unique competencies, which this person can bring into your collaboration, are: **complex systems, math, engineering.**

Pitched: My dream is to create machines that talk!

How to use a mohawk: or me on IIB 😊

Me contacting individuals [independent professionals]:

- On my behalf _____
- On behalf of my collaboration _____

Me contacting collaborations

Me being contacted:

- By other individuals [independent professionals]
- By collaborations

+ Conversations in my collaborations

+ My everybody

What can that give to you? That is the fun part: surprises.

But! You must be a person of integrity and respect other people. Don't steal, don't cheat. Behave decent.

I regularly update the General Instruction and News.

Expected impact of IIB

Increase in the capacity of risk taking by people: max 35% of people can accept risk, and IIB will raise it to appr. 70%

Raise in the number of emerging technologies: since that is one of the key targets, then by 65%, considering the inertia

Disruption of HR as a business branch: 0% of HR involvement is required for this h2h solution

Emergence of more conscious and stable collaborations with solid visions: 60% of raise in this will be a success

Larger number of organically self-organizing hybrid-knowledge initiatives: since high-performers comprise only 20% of the population in an enterprise, and we will make them more visible to each other and the eventual 20% of high-performers among independent professionals, they will be able to collaborate with emergent effectiveness of appr. 75%

And that is targeting the international level.

IIB is in English and uses the principles of humor universality deduced in Humor Science. Most of the jokes in IIB are originally Russian as of now, but the UX participants say “The humor was too American...”

I am glad, very glad. Bond, James Bond. Damme, Van Damme, Claude Van Damme, Jean-Claude Van Damme.

What other people write to me about IIB

A business strategy consultant & ecosystem facilitator, self-employed freelancer, collaborator at the Systems Innovation London Hub: *“Your work sounds fascinating, I like the sound of Wise Jester bringing AI to something I often contemplate as a problem – people being separated by hierarchies or indeed worldviews. I'm curious to see how it emerges.”*

A CEO of a blockchain-powered company in plastic waste recycling and owner of the Oslo Blockchain Cluster: *“If I want to go into this to find a fun collaboration or a collaborator who are anonymous, and to see who is qualified, it would be great to see a list of “secret projects” I did not know about and might become a part of. It would be interesting to join those networks, unknown, and anonymously be able to help someone and get rewarded somehow. Maybe I could find people from Google to join me, let say, for an hour per week, so I can get some advice.”*

An UX designer and consultant with international background: *“It is a really special project. It is really cool and really novel. It feels like you are very playful, and this project is very playful. I can see it attracting a certain type of people. That is usually how cool, innovative things work, right? It is not for the general public. It is like with the first smartphone. Weird nerds, technology nerds who were interested. I have an impression that the system will be interesting for very special companies: startups or freelancers, companies that are fed up with their recruitment systems, because it takes too much time, and it is too expensive.”*

In June we added “Pitch yourself”/“Pitch your collaboration” [“Pitched”], and in July we add a complex real-time chat.

More complex and new is ahead!

TEAM Wise Jester

Anna Zaytseva, founder: IIB concept, humor work, logic, contents, communication, fundraising

~~David William Tann, co-founder: stage comedy, English, interest in distributed architectures~~

I keep on looking and networking. I will pick co-founders from the growing IIB userbase by Oct. '21.

Here are my contractual and supporting collaborators:

Alexey Egoshin, contractual developer: user interface, human-computer interaction

Massimo Stella, invited scientist: systems science, psycholinguistics

7bulls, contractual developers: statistics, upscaling, tests

Rock music, style: inspiration

If you wish to become a piece of jester, let me know! 😊

wisejester@intellectualandimmaterialbank.com

IIB is online, and we are UX improving it. Please, create your user in the IIB system and give us your feedback. We will be UX improving IIB from now on and forever.

And we are looking for bright investors!

<https://intellectualandimmaterialbank.com>

***Cordially,
Anna A. Zaytseva,
Founder of Wise Jester AS.***